

Supplementary Tutorial

The rPesca package is designed to guide users through a dynamic workflow that interacts with the user via prompts. Below is a detailed step-by-step guide on how to use the package.

1. Prerequisites for Installation

- It is recommended to use RStudio for a more user-friendly experience.
- Ensure that either the devtools or remotes package is installed.

To install the rPesca package, use one of the following commands:

- If you have devtools installed:

```
devtools::install_github("FelipeCadilho/rPesca")
```

- If you have remotes installed:

```
remotes::install_github("FelipeCadilho/rPesca")
```

2. Data Requirements

Your data file must include:

- First column: Age data.
- Second column: Length data.
- Third column: Categorical gender classification (e.g., male or female).

The file can be in .xls, .xlsx, .csv, .txt formats, or an R dataframe object. If using .csv or .txt formats, you need to specify the column separator (e.g., comma or space).

3. Setting the Working Directory

Before running rPesca, set your working directory to the location where your data file is stored.

- Example command:

```
setwd("C:/Users/YourUsername/Documents")
```

- Alternatively, you can set the working directory via the Files tab in RStudio.

4. Loading the Package and Running the Main Function

Load the package and execute the main function:

- Load the package:

```
library(rPesca)
```

- Run the main function rPesca():

```
rPesca()
```

5. Function Parameters

The rPesca() function accepts several parameters for customization:

- cores: Numeric, determines the color scale for graphs (1 = grayscale, 2 = color). Default: grayscale.
- idioma: Numeric, defines the language (1 = Portuguese, 2 = English). Default: Portuguese.
- un: Numeric, sets the unit of length (1 = cm, 2 = mm, 3 = m). Default: cm.
- tipoComprimento: Character, specifies the type of length measurement (e.g., "Total" for Total Length).
- tempo: Numeric, sets the time unit for age (1 = year, 2 = month, 3 = day). Default: year.
- tipo_dados: Numeric, defines the data file format (1 = .xls/.xlsx, 2 = .csv, 3 = .txt, 4 = dataframe). Default: dataframe.
- nome_dados: Character, specifies the name of the data file (required).
- planilha: Character, specifies the sheet name in the .xls/.xlsx file. Default: first sheet.
- separador: Character, sets the separator for .csv or .txt files (e.g., comma , or space). Default: comma.
- grupo: Numeric, sets group analysis (1 = yes, empty = no).
- nomeA: Character, specifies the name for group A (required for group analysis).
- nomeB: Character, specifies the name for group B (required for group analysis).

Example usage:

- Without specifying parameter names:

```
rPesca(2, 2, 1, "Total", 1, 4, ex_individual)
```

- With parameter names:

```
rPesca(cores = 2, idioma = 2, un = 1, tipoComprimento = "Total", tempo = 1, tipo_dados = 4, nome_dados = ex_individual)
```

6. Answering Prompts

As the function runs, the program will prompt the user with questions regarding the analysis. Respond to these prompts to customize the analysis according to your specific needs. The program will guide you step-by-step.

7. Mortality Calculations

It is possible to calculate total mortality outside the main routine using the `mortalidadeZ()` function. Ensure your dataset is properly formatted with age or length classes.

- By Age:

```
mortalidadeZ(c_infinito = 60.44, k = 0.19, tzero = -0.74, dataframe, idioma = 1, adhoc = 2)
```

- By Length:

```
mortalidadeZ(c_infinito = 60.44, k = 0.19, tzero = -0.74, dataframe, idioma = 1, adhoc = 1)
```

Ensure that you provide the required growth parameters `c_infinito`, `k`, and `tzero` to calculate the mortality rates correctly.